

Non-synaptic encoding of behavior by neuropeptides

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8 **Abstract**

9 A basic tenet of neuroscience is that animal behavior is generated by neural circuits that operate through
10 synaptic transmission. On top of this synaptic “chassis” of nervous systems, neuropeptides and hor-
11 mones have traditionally been considered as slow neuromodulatory signals that fine-tune synaptic cir-
12 cuits. However, neuropeptides can generate many behaviors, including quite complex ones, from cnidar-
13 ians to humans. Moreover, neuropeptide actions span larger temporal scales than fast synaptic transmis-
14 sion and are thus better matched to behavioral time courses than synaptic circuits. Furthermore, in some
15 metazoans, the effects of neuropeptides are independent of synaptic connectivity and in many species
16 the systemic application of neuropeptides can trigger selective behaviors. Based on this, we argue
17 that non-synaptic neuropeptide signaling via chemical networks—forming a “chemical” connectome—
18 represent the ancestral mechanism to encode behavioral sequences, whereas synaptic networks co-
19 evolved as a specialization complementing chemical networks in the control of behaviors and computa-
20 tional functions.

21 **Synaptic transmission as the “chassis” of the nervous system**

22 One of the seminal moments in neuroscience happened in 1888 in Spain when a young assistant pro-
23 fessor, Santiago Ramon y Cajal, described dendritic spines, small structures that cover the dendrites of
24 most neurons in the brain. A few years later, Cajal proposed that spines receive contacts from axons
25 of other neurons and extended the idea to his neuron doctrine, that states that the nervous system is
26 composed of individual neurons that do not touch each other, but communicate through a small gap
27 between the axon and the dendritic spines [1]. In 1897, Charles Sherrington [2] generalized the idea to
28 all neuronal connections and coined the term “synapse” to refer to that gap where axons and dendrites
29 communicate.

30 The proposal of a synapse had to wait half a century for confirmation until the development of electron
31 microscopy. In 1956, independent studies from De Robertis' and Palay's laboratories demonstrated that
32 Cajal was indeed right, and that synapses are the site of communication between neurons [3,4]. They
33 provided ultrastructural evidence for the presence of presynaptic terminals with vesicles that are released
34 into a small synaptic gap. This discovery, together with the isolation of neurotransmitters started by Otto
35 Loewi [5] and the biophysical examination of synaptic function in the neuromuscular junction pioneered by
36 Bernard Katz and his group [6,7] made the synapse the cornerstone of neuroscience, fueling decades of
37 research understanding how synapses are involved in neuronal communication, circuit function, behavior,
38 learning and plasticity, and pathological processes.

39 Synapses provide many advantages for the nervous system. First, they allow the amplification of sig-
40 nals from a single neuron, since action potentials in an axon can reach and activate tens of thousands
41 of synapses, spreading the information to a large number of recipient cells. Also, because of the high
42 speed of action potential propagation as they traverse the axon and the short diffusional delays asso-
43 ciated with synaptic release, this strategy also ensures fast signaling between neurons. Importantly,
44 synapses also allow for selective targeting of neuronal partners, and in fact, axonal pathfinding is one
45 of the most distinct aspects of the development of the nervous system, generating a specific connec-
46 tivity matrix. This specific connectivity, many people think, is the essence of the brain and what gives
47 it its functional properties. Correspondingly, efforts to systematically map the wiring diagram of neural
48 circuits using connectomics have become a natural approach to decipher neuronal computations. More-
49 over, synapses can be excitatory or inhibitory, thus providing the possibility of creating neuronal circuits
50 with sophisticated computational logic. The existing of recurrent connections with excitatory synapses
51 also enables the creation of circuit attractors that could be used to implement computational or mental
52 states, including cognitive processes. Synapses have also other advantages, as they can be modulated
53 by external signals and precisely fine-tuned, but there are also major mysteries about their function. For
54 example, transmission in most synapses is stochastic, meaning that they not always activate when re-
55 ceiving an action potential, and it is still not well understood why the brain uses stochastic processes in
56 the fundamental channel of communication between neurons.

57 **Chemical signaling in the nervous system**

58 While there is no question that synapses are critical features of the nervous system, it is interesting
59 to remember that, historically, there were also other hypotheses to explain how neurons communicate.
60 Already in the 1920's, Paul Weiss argued against the "connectionist view" anchored on synapses and
61 proposed instead that neurons could communicate by specific chemical signals, which, like a radio broad-
62 cast, would diffuse through the nervous system and be detected by a specific chemical receptors in the
63 target cells. Thus, specific communication between neurons could occur in the absence of synaptic trans-
64 mission [8,9]. The discovery of neuroendocrine hormones [10], most of which were peptides, secreted
65 in an endocrine (blood-based) or paracrine (volume transmission) manner, together with the diffuse ac-
66 tions of many neurotransmitters like acetylcholine, norepinephrine, serotonin and dopamine, provided
67 evidence that supported the view of Weiss for many physiological processes. But, in general, the non-
68 synaptic forms of neuronal communications were considered accessory to synaptic transmission, and

69 many of these systems were correspondingly labeled as “neuromodulators”.

70 The underestimation of the potential of non-synaptic chemical signaling was partly a result of the compar-
71 ison between the slow diffusion of chemical signals and the fast axonal conduction and neurotransmitter
72 release. But chemical signaling can be very quick, particularly in systems where diffusion is bi- or even
73 unidimensional, like in the synaptic cleft, in membrane-based biochemistry or in tubular systems. Also,
74 the intuition of most biologists about chemical reactions are based on studies at chemical equilibrium,
75 relying on bulk or average dynamics of molecules, which is correspondingly slow. However, most bio-
76 logical reactions likely follow non-equilibrium kinetics, which can be much faster, and generate chemical
77 dynamics that are complex and non-intuitive. For example, it is possible to generate oscillations using
78 coupled non-linear kinetic equations [11] and, by combining a set of oscillators, like in a Fourier trans-
79 form, one can in principle generate any temporal pattern of activity. This means that the generation of
80 temporally-structured neuronal activity, as is required for any behavior, could arise from chemical sig-
81 nals, like neuropeptides, secreted by neurons in an oscillatory fashion [12]. In fact, oscillatory dynamics
82 of the GnRH/LH hormones can be generated in the hypothalamus, leading to pulsed secretion [13]. Also,
83 although diffusional equilibrium kinetics are slow in a volume, the diffusional arrival of individual effec-
84 tor molecules to their receptor in non-equilibrium conditions can be surprisingly rapid, according to the
85 narrow escape theory of Brownian particles [14]. Moreover, chemical positive feedback loops by self-
86 stimulation can effectively serve like a chemical action potential to generate a regenerative chemical
87 signal that reaches the entire nervous system quickly [12].

88 Another common misunderstanding of chemical signaling is that it lacks targeting specificity. But the
89 specificity of endocrine or paracrine extracellular chemical signals can be achieved by the selective
90 expression of receptors in target cells. Moreover, a common theme in biology is the large variety of
91 receptor structures, affinities, dynamics and effectors, generated by differences in receptor sequences,
92 binding properties, the differential processing of receptors or multimerization. If one adds to this a similar
93 richness in the variety of chemical signaling molecules, particularly with neuropeptides, that are often
94 preprocessed selectively, one could generate chemical networks with an enormous combinatorial space
95 of selective interactions.

96 Thus, many of the features of synaptic networks can also be achieved with chemical networks. Moreover,
97 chemical networks do not rely on the existence of a physical wiring, which could be difficult to set up and
98 maintain, particularly in animals that lack a skeleton and are subject to significant deformations of their
99 body during behavior. The lack of a wiring constrain could also protect the nervous system against
100 physical damage and enable scaling to match the size of the body of the animal, which could be a
101 quite significant problem during development and also in species that can have more than an order of
102 magnitude variation in body size during their lifetime, depending on nutrition, like cnidarians. Finally, not
103 relying on a wiring diagram for their function could make nervous systems more adaptable and make it
104 easier to evolve different behaviors.

105 **Evolution of neuropeptide-receptor networks across animals**

106 Within all the chemical signals used by neurons, neuropeptides, secreted signaling molecules ubiquitous
107 across animals, stand out. They are abundant in all animals with a nervous system and have even been

108 identified in the neuron-less placozoans, animals consisting of two ciliated contractile epithelia.

109 Generally, active neuropeptides are produced from inactive precursors that are cleaved in the secretory
110 apparatus. Smaller peptide fragments can then be modified by amidation, pyroglutamylation, isomeriza-
111 tion and other forms of post-translational modification [15] to give rise to the biologically active peptides.
112 Often, variants of similar peptides are produced from the same precursor. The mature peptides are then
113 released from dense core vesicles (vesicles with a characteristic dark appearance on electron microscopy
114 images) from somata, along dendrites (at synapses or en passant) or at specialised neuro-haemal re-
115 lease sites (e.g. pituitary gland).

116 Neuropeptide precursors are highly diverse in animals with bilaterian genomes commonly encoding many
117 dozen and sometimes over 100 propeptides [16–18]. Since many precursors contain multiple divergent
118 peptides, the diversity of bioactive ligands is even larger. Similar peptides released from the same pre-
119 cursor can have different potency of receptor activation [17,19], further diversifying outputs.

120 A similar diversity is encountered in neuropeptide receptors. Most of these belong to the G-protein
121 coupled receptors (GPCRs) and we limit our focus to this family, although they are also other types of
122 receptor molecules [19–21]. Animal genomes commonly encode several hundred GPCRs, with a large
123 fraction of these being receptors for neuropeptides [17,18]. Systematic reverse pharmacological stud-
124 ies of receptor-ligand pairs across animals revealed a similar organisation of receptor-ligand networks
125 [17,18,22]. Individual neuropeptides can activate one to many GPCRs, while GPCRs in general are
126 activated by only one type of peptide (including its variants). For example, a recent large-scale study
127 in *C. elegans* documented extensive cross-talk between RFamide peptides and one family of extended
128 receptors [17].

129 **Neuropeptides provide chemical fingerprints to neurons**

130 The advent of single-cell RNA sequencing has enabled mapping of cellular and gene expression diver-
131 sity across a large number of animals and tissues, providing quantitative new insights into the age-old
132 question of what constitutes a neuronal cell type. A recurrent finding from these studies has been the
133 specific expression of neuropeptide precursor genes in neurons. Neuropeptide genes are highly and
134 selectively expressed in distinct neuronal cell types, as defined by the cluster analysis of expression pro-
135 files. Indeed, neuropeptides and their receptors sharply demarcate even the finest cell type distinctions,
136 providing a combinatorial code that, together with the combination of homeodomain transcription factors,
137 is currently the best descriptor of neuronal identity [23–26]. The specific expression of neuropeptides
138 and receptors in different cell types has been found from the mammalian cortex [24] through *C. elegans*
139 [23] to the ctenophore aboral organ [26]. The fact that a large fraction of neuronal cell types expresses a
140 distinct combination of neuropeptides suggests that they give each neuron a specific chemical signature,
141 much like a fingerprint. When a neuron is activated, these neuropeptides could be co-released from the
142 same dense core vesicle pool [27]. Since neuropeptide GPCRs show a similar specific and combina-
143 torial expression, each peptide cocktail could influence a specific set of target neurons expressing one
144 of the matching receptors. The totality of such potential connections is referred to as the “chemical” or
145 “peptidergic” connectome [18,28–31] (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Reconstruction of peptidergic networks in the cnidarian *Nematostella vectensis*. (A) Transgenic labeling of neurons expressing an LWamide neuropeptide. (B-C) Ligand activation curves of a *Nematostella* RPamide (B) and FLRNamide (C) receptor activated by two different peptides with different dose-response relationships. (D) Bipartite neuropeptide-GPCR interaction networks for all known *Nematostella* peptidergic signaling pairs. (E) Cellular signaling networks between LRWamide-expressing cells and cells expressing one of four LRWamide receptors. Edges are colored by receptor type in the target cell. Modified from [18,32].

146 **Neuropeptide-receptor networks are organised into multilayer chemical connectomes**

147 Systematic expression and receptor deorphanisation studies have begun to reveal cellular-resolution
148 multilayer peptidergic connectomes for entire organs or organisms [18,24,28–31]. In such chemical
149 networks, individual neurons, or neuron types, are the nodes whereas links are defined by the expression
150 of neuropeptides and their receptors. A link represents the potential of a peptide-producing cell to signal
151 to a cell expressing a receptor for that peptide. Due to the diversity of peptide-receptor pairs, such
152 chemical connectomes are organised into multiple layers that can be overlaid, or not, on the synaptic and
153 gap-junction connectomes. All these chemical layers are invisible to EM-based reconstructions, forming,
154 as if it were, the ‘dark matter’ of connectomics, as they cannot currently be detected by ultrastructural
155 methods.

156 One of the most difficult and intriguing challenges in connectomics and neuroscience will be to disentangle
157 how these multiple layers interact with each other to lead to neuronal dynamics and behavior. Below,
158 we will discuss examples of peptide-driven behaviors across animals starting with the non-bilaterian placozoans,
159 cnidarians and ctenophores.

160 **Non-synaptic coordination of behavior by neuropeptides in basal metazoans**

161 The study of non-bilaterian metazoan species supports a critical role of neuropeptides in the nervous
162 system and have provided an interesting perspective to understand the evolution of neuronal signaling.
163 These animals—unlike bilaterians—mostly show rotational symmetry. Non-bilaterians include iridescent
164 comb-jellies or ctenophores (Ctenophora), filter-feeding sponges (Porifera), flat neuron-less placozoans
165 (Placozoa), and cnidarians such as jellyfish, sea anemones, corals and relatives (Cnidaria). We will
166 discuss these groups, with the exception of sponges that lack a nervous system and only have a few
167 neuropeptide-like molecules [33].

168 **Ctenophores**

169 Ctenophores, or comb jellies, are likely the most distant relatives of all other animals. They have a nervous
170 system with many characteristics that are thought to have evolved independently from other animals.
171 These include a syncytial nerve net, peculiar synapse morphologies, and lack of most canonical neurotransmitters
172 [34–36]. Ctenophore genomes also encode a large number of proneuropeptides that are
173 unrelated to the peptides of placozoans, cnidarians or bilaterians [26,37]. Indeed, also in ctenophores,
174 neuropeptides are among the most highly expressed and specific markers of neurons [26,38]. Their receptors
175 and functions are largely unexplored, but the available evidence suggests a strong peptidergic
176 character for their nervous organisation. For example, the ctenophore aboral or apical organ contains
177 a rich repertoire of sensory-peptidergic cells marked by the cell-type-specific expression of many neuropeptides
178 [26]. The connectomics reconstructions of this region in *Mnemiopsis leidyi* revealed that
179 these sensory cells do not have presynaptic sites (Jokura, Burkhardt and GJ, unpublished), suggesting
180 that they may communicate via chemical diffusion of neuropeptides.

181 Placozoans

182 A fascinating organism that can help reveal fundamental principles and processes of peptidergic control
183 is the placozoan *Trichoplax adhaerens* and its relatives. Placozoans are neuron-less and muscle-less
184 animals that glide on a ciliated ventral epithelium and feed by extracellular digestion on algal mats [39].
185 There are no canonical neurons with axons and dendrites in these animals and no synapses were de-
186 tectable by either light or electron microscopy. Yet, again, placozoans express a high number of proneu-
187 ropeptides (27) and many of these are specific to distinct cell types [40,41]. Bath-application of some
188 of the processed peptides to the animals induces dramatic shape changes (e.g. flattening, crinkling,
189 rounding-up), likely by accentuating elements of tissue movement that would play out in behavioral se-
190 quences in untreated animals [40] (Figure 2). Some of the behaviors induced by peptides are periodic,
191 suggesting a more complex signaling dynamics that includes feedbacks. Behavioral studies have docu-
192 mented chemotaxis [39], thermotaxis [42], collective feeding [43], fast epithelial contractions propagating
193 in waves [44], churning movement during feeding and other behaviors [39,45]. A large-scale pharmaco-
194 logical screen identified 19 placozoan neuropeptide GPCRs that independently radiated from cnidarian
195 and bilaterian neuropeptide receptors (Yañez-Guerra and GJ, unpublished). Given the lack of neural
196 circuits, a current model is that placozoan behaviors are coordinated through the release of peptides or
197 peptide mixtures (and possibly other small chemicals) that play out various patterns of activity on the
198 spatial and temporal scale of the behavioral patterns [40,46].

Figure 2: **Figure 2. Peptidergic control of behavior in the synapse-less animal *Trichoplax adhaerens*.** (A) Immunostaining for SIFG, SIF and FFNP neuropeptides in *T. adhaerens*. (B) Bath application of SIF peptide causes the rapid crinkling of the animals. (C) Bath application of WPPF neuropeptide induces the periodic flattening of the animals (modified from [40]).

199 Cnidarians

200 Cnidaria is the sister phylum to the bilaterians and their comparative study is therefore most informative
201 to understand the evolutionary origins of bilaterian nervous systems [47,48]. There has been recent
202 progress in characterising nervous organisation and neuropeptide signaling in these animals. Bioinfor-
203 matic and sensitive mass spectrometry methods have allowed the assembly of comprehensive lists of
204 the neuropeptide repertoire of several species [18,37,49]. The best studied species is the anthozoan
205 *Nematostella vectensis*, a widely studied model cnidarian (Figure 1). *Nematostella* has over 30 proneu-
206 ropeptides that give rise to at least twice as many peptides. Many of these have been experimentally
207 detected by mass spectrometry [18,37,50] and the expressing neurons form nerve nets [32,51]. A recent

208 large-scale deorphanisation screen identified 31 GPCRs activated by one of 14 peptides [18]. As in other
209 animals, the proneuropeptides are specifically expressed in diverse neurons and combinations of them
210 can be used as neuronal identity markers. The receptors also show specific expression in neurons and
211 other tissue types (e.g., muscles, germ cells)[18].

212 Among hydrozoans—the other major branch of cnidarians—a different class of receptors have been
213 discovered. The freshwater *Hydra*—also a popular model organism—has peptide-gated ion channels
214 of the DEG/ENaC family, activated by RFamide peptides [20,52,53]. The channels are trimeric and
215 different combinations are activated by different peptides and to different degree. There are about a
216 dozen monomers encoded in the genome of *Hydra* and other cnidarians, with the ability to form several
217 distinct trimeric channels [20].

218 What is the function of neuropeptide signaling in cnidarians? Some peptides are released by sensory
219 stimulation, such as the Maturation-Inducing Hormones (MIH) or PRXamide peptides in the jellyfish *Clytia*
220 and other hydrozoans [54]. MIH is produced by opsin-expressing light-sensory cells in the epithelium of
221 the *Clytia* gonad in neurons that form a nerve net [51]. Light at dawn activates these cells to release their
222 peptide content. The peptides then activate a MIH-receptor expressed in the oocytes, triggering oocyte
223 maturation and release [55].

224 In *Hydra*, the neuropeptide Hym-248 can trigger somersaulting, a fixed action pattern characterized by or-
225 ganized and sequential tentacle and body movements [12] (Figure 3). Hym-248 is expressed in rhythmic
226 potential 1 neurons (RP1), which are activated by the very same peptide they release, and this positive
227 feedback loop generates a “chemical” action potential, which quickly reaches the entire nervous system.
228 Thus, RP1 neurons form a network throughout the body of the animal with all-or-not activation, leading to
229 their widespread release of Hym-248. The activation of RP1 neurons induces somersaulting and their ab-
230 lation abolishes it. Confirming their causal role in this behavior, bath application of Hym-248 also induces
231 somersaulting, by triggering that complex body-wide sequence of responses through acting on many dif-
232 ferent cell types [12]. How the precise action sequence emerges from these interactions still remains
233 unclear. Nevertheless, these results demonstrate that peptide action may play out at different temporal
234 and spatial scales to bring about a complex sequence of activity changes, such as somersaulting.

Figure 3: **Figure 3. Neuropeptides mediate somersaulting in the cnidarian *Hydra vulgaris*.** (A-B) Sequential stages of somersaulting behavior in a free behaving *Hydra*. (C) Bath application of Hym-248 triggers somersaulting. (D) Postulated circuit model for somersaulting with cross-inhibition between RP1 and CB neuronal ensembles and release of the neuropeptide Hym-248 (modified from [12]).

235 Neuropeptide signaling in bilaterian invertebrates

236 Similarly to non-bilaterian metazoans, there are several reports of non-synaptic effects of neuropeptides,
 237 or even traditional transmitters, in bilaterians. This has been particularly demonstrated in invertebrate
 238 preparations. An early example was reported in an electron microscopy study of the sea urchin *Strongy-*
 239 *locentrotus franciscanus* [56]. This echinoderm has no demonstrated neuromuscular synapses or axons
 240 that connect the nerve plexus with the muscle fibers, suggesting that chemical diffusion of acetylcholine,
 241 as opposed to its synaptic release, mediates neuromuscular transmission.

242 A more recent study in *C. elegans* characterised a staggering 461 neuropeptide-GPCR interactions [17].
 243 These can be activated by a host of neuropeptides derived from 58 precursors. This in principle means
 244 that the nematode nervous system could have at least 461 peptidergic layers in its chemical connectome.

245 Moreover, a quantitative whole-brain analysis of neuron-to-neuron activity propagation in the *C. elegans*
 246 nervous system found a significant mismatch between the synaptic and functional connectivity, and pro-
 247 posed that this mismatch could be explained if many functional interactions were non-synaptically me-
 248 diated by neuropeptides [57]. This study used calcium imaging as a readout of neuronal activity and
 249 therefore likely underestimates the extent of peptidergic signaling (also acting via cAMP and other path-
 250 ways). If we assume that any behavior requires the propagation of activity by a network of neurons, it is
 251 likely that peptides are involved in most behaviors in the worm, except maybe the most hard-wired ones,
 252 like the startle circuit. Indeed, in the worm, peptides have been shown to be essential or rate-limiting in
 253 foraging, feeding, mating, oviposition, learning, nociception, social behavior, etc. [58–66].

254 Another invertebrate example where neuropeptides play a major role is the marine annelid *Platynereis*
 255 *dumerilii*, which has an anterior neurosecretory region expressing over 50 different neuropeptide genes
 256 in a cell-type-specific manner [29] (Figure 4). Many neurons in the region are sensory-neurosecretory
 257 neurons with no or very few presynaptic sites. Indeed, bath-application of peptides effects swimming be-
 258 havior, often by the modulation of a pacemaker circuit for ciliary closures [67–69]. Some peptides have
 259 more wide-ranging behavioral effects in *Platynereis*. Application of the conserved myoinhibitory peptide

260 (MIP)[70] inhibits ciliary activity, induces surface-exploratory behavior and at later stages promotes feed-
261 ing [68,71]. MIP is expressed in sensory-neurosecretory cells with few synapses and its actions are likely
262 largely extrasynaptic. Two different MIP receptors have been identified, a GPCR and a peptide-gated
263 channel [19], both with complex expression patterns. The actions of MIP likely play out at very different
264 temporal scales, from the millisecond to the hours scale and include the change of ionic conductance,
265 second messenger pathways and gene-expression changes (E.A. Williams and GJ, unpublished). Some
266 of its targets are synaptic circuits (through the ion channel) but others seem to be other neuroendocrine
267 cells (through the GPCR), potentially triggering peptide “cascades”, i.e., sequential activation of neurons
268 via neuropeptides. These chemical networks of neuropeptides are fascinating and complex, revealing
269 a rich system of organized interactions between neurons that escape the description of their synaptic
270 connectivity.

Figure 4: **Figure 4. Peptidergic networks in the marine annelid *Platynereis dumerilii*.** (A) Scanning electron micrograph of a three-day-old *P. dumerilii* larva (scale bar, 50 μm). (B-C) Morphological rendering of sensory-neurosecretory cells in the anterior nervous system of a three-day-old larva based on volume EM reconstructions, ventral (B) and anterior (C) views. (D) Synaptic and chemical networks. In synaptic networks, the specific activation of an effector neuron (bottom black) by a command neuron (top black) is mediated by a series of neuronal intermediaries, activated via synaptic transmission. In chemical networks, the diffusion of a neuropeptide (arrow) released by the command neuron reaches the effector neuron, which is the only neuron that has the appropriate receptor. (E) signaling networks of myomodulin neuropeptide reaching two different subsets of target cells at different distances expressing one of two myomodulin receptors. Individual nodes represent cells from a single-cell RNA sequencing resource [72] that were spatially mapped to the anatomy of the larval brain. Myomodulin expression is shown in blue, receptor expression in red (modified from [29]).

271 One of the most remarkable examples of the function of neuropeptide cascades in controlling a complex
272 behavioral sequence in invertebrates is ecdysis (moulting of the cuticles) in flies [73]. In *Drosophila*
273 *melanogaster*, a series of neuropeptides including kinin, FMRFamides, eclosion hormone (EH) and MIP
274 act in a sequence to coordinate the distinct steps of ecdysis [73]. Upstream peptides drive the early
275 phases of the behavior and also trigger the release of downstream peptides that coordinate the next
276 step in the behavioral sequence [74]. Breaking the signaling chain by cell ablations or mutations in
277 some of the peptides breaks the ecdysis sequence at specific points [74,75]. In this case, as in *Hydra*
278 somersaulting, neuropeptides thus have an essential non-modulatory function in determining the precise
279 sequence of a behavior [74].

280 **Neuropeptide signaling in bilaterian vertebrates**

281 There are also many reports of the importance of neuropeptides in the generation of behavior in ver-
282 tebrates. In fact, some of the best examples of the existence of a causal link between molecules and
283 behavior are due to neuropeptides, even for quite sophisticated behaviors like social interactions [76] or
284 effects as specific as stress-induced analgesia [77]. Even in humans, neuropeptides such as kisspeptin
285 [78], orexin [79] or oxytocin [80,] have been demonstrated to regulate complex behaviors. From a large
286 literature we highlight the example of oxytocin and vasopressin, released into the blood from the posterior
287 pituitary, and which can mediate mammalian behaviors as selective as bonding with mates and offspring.
288 In mice, for example, oxytocin is necessary and sufficient for the social recognition of individual members
289 of the species [81,82].

290 A particularly salient example of the role of oxytocin and vasopressin is reported in studies of the prairie
291 vole *Microtus ochrogaster*, which form stable mating pairs that raise their progeny. The release of oxy-
292 tocin in female voles due to physical contact during mating stimulates pair-bond formation [83]. Similar
293 effects are achieved by the systemic application of oxytocin [84]. Meanwhile, in the male, the release
294 of vasopressin also stimulates pair bonding and paternal behavior and the systemic application of vaso-
295 pressin or a receptor blocker directly affects this behavior [85]. Even in humans, oxytocin and vasopressin
296 may be necessary for sexual behavior, paternal behavior, and pair bonding [86]. Thus, some of our most
297 significant behavioral decisions and actions could be mediated by the systemic effect of neuropeptides.

298 While the effects of neuropeptides in vertebrates are generally interpreted to occur via their local modu-
299 lation of synaptic networks, the fact that they are often released systemically in the vascular system and
300 that systemic applications of them trigger the generation of behavior agrees with the above-mentioned
301 design logic of systemic effects of neuropeptides found in non-bilaterians metazoans and invertebrates.
302 In fact, just like in non-bilaterians, dense neuropeptide networks can be revealed from the analysis of
303 single-cell transcriptomics in the mammalian cortex, arguably, the paradigmatic example of synaptic
304 circuits [24]. Finally, while there is clear evidence in mammalian systems of large-scale systemic release
305 of neuropeptides over long time scales, there is still a paucity of results describing local peptidergic sig-
306 naling that is temporally acute, as is evident in many invertebrate systems. At this point, it is unclear
307 if the differences between systemic and local effects of neuropeptides between vertebrate and inverte-
308 brate preparations are due to evolutionary differences, or are simply a result of our current lack of data
309 on neuropeptide networks and cascades.

310 **A peptidergic origin of nervous systems**

311 Comparing the molecular machinery of peptide processing and release in peptidergic cells reveals strong
312 similarities across animals [37,41]. This, together with the identification of some neuropeptides con-
313 served in all animals [33] indicates that the last metazoan common ancestor likely already used peptides
314 for intercellular signaling [87]. Since so far one has encountered the same logic to neural peptide sig-
315 naling in all animals, including specificity of expression in neuronal cells and a combinatorial code of
316 neuron identity, we propose that the first animals used peptides as a chemical fingerprint of neurons, to
317 trigger the activation of a specific combination of receptors in a set of target cells and generate a behavior.
318 Since any behavioral sequence requires the activation of a specific subset of cells (e.g., neurons, mus-
319 cles, glands, ciliated cells etc.) in a specific spatial and temporal sequence, neuropeptides are ideally
320 suited to molecularly encode such activation patterns. While synaptic networks could in principle pro-
321 vide the same cell-to-cell specificity, emerging evidence from non-bilaterians suggests that nerve-nets
322 are organised following different principles. For example, the nerve nets in *Hydra*, the *Clytia* gonad or
323 ctenophores seem to extend to cover a large area to ensure the widespread propagation of coordinated
324 activity and corresponding peptide release [36,51]. There is currently no evidence that these nerve nets
325 provide specific innervation of target cells or form a complex recurrent multilayer architecture, necessary
326 for synaptic circuits to operate and generate complex behavioral patterns. In contrast, the high molec-
327 ular diversity for peptides and peptide receptors and their specific expression patterns ideally position
328 these systems to connect cells into multilayer networks with specific connections, with the possibility of
329 activation and inhibition or recurrent signaling. In this view of early nervous systems, the ‘connectome’
330 is provided by peptides, whereas synapses only form a global repetitive network to send and integrate
331 signals across body parts and coordinate neuropeptide release.

332 Indeed, neuropeptide action can also play out on different time and spatial scales. This is due to the pos-
333 sibility of diffusion of peptides away from their release sites. While for small neurotransmitters, specific
334 and rapid reuptake and degradation pathways exist and are essential for normal function, no equivalent
335 system is known for neuropeptides. The presence of multiple receptors with different sensitivities for
336 the same peptide, as is often the case, suggest that peptides may act at different distances and with
337 different temporal dynamics. For example, in *C. elegans*, peptides can activate GPCRs that are far from
338 their release site [28,88].

339 As mentioned above, neuropeptides could also generate sophisticated temporal patterns of activation in
340 target cells. The on and off rate of receptor binding, the nature of the intracellular pathway activated by the
341 receptor or the speed of receptor internalisation could all influence signaling dynamics. Little is known
342 about the precise kinetics of peptide-receptor pairs and intuition is often misleading. From molecular
343 pharmacology, we know that some GPCR ligands can have residence times of minutes to hours [89–91].
344 In addition, peptide-GPCR signaling in the nervous system is happening at non-equilibrium dynamics, as
345 mentioned above. Thus, peptide action can happen at a variety of spatial and temporal scales that are
346 very different from the millisecond-scale of action potentials and synaptic transmission and more closely
347 matches the timescale of most behaviors.

348 One could argue that peptides would only activate a certain synaptic circuit, e.g. by pushing it through a
349 threshold, and the specific spatial-temporal pattern of activation would follow due to synaptic connectivity.

350 This is certainly possible in many cases, however, we suggest that, from the above examples and likely
351 many other cases, the role of peptides is more complex than a simple trigger of synaptic circuits and
352 their actions are essential for the spatio-temporal choreography of behaviors.

353 **The “hard” neuropeptide hypothesis: molecular encoding of behavior**

354 The above examples demonstrate the importance of neuropeptides as coordinators of behavioral se-
355 quences in many different species. As mentioned, some of the best examples of a neurobiological expla-
356 nation of behavior feature neuropeptides [76]. Since neuropeptides are often co-released at synapses
357 [92], these results are consistent with the traditional view that synaptic circuits mediate behavior, with
358 neuropeptides playing an adjuvant role, and modifying the synaptic effects of traditional transmitters. We
359 term this the “*soft*” *neuropeptide hypothesis*, where neuropeptides would act synaptically and resembles
360 the “broadcast” mechanism of Weiss. But this paradigm is being challenged by an increasing number
361 of examples where the action of neuropeptides appears not to rely on synaptic transmission. This is ap-
362 parent in some of the above-mentioned studies on non-bilaterian metazoans and simpler animal model
363 systems, perhaps because it is easier to assemble a comprehensive datasets on the entire nervous
364 system. In many of these preparations, ultrastructural evidence of synapses is scant and often unclear
365 [93]. For example, in *Hydra*’s endodermal nerve net, synaptic vesicles are found in parts of the neuron lo-
366 cated far away from potential neuronal partners, as if the content of vesicles were acting non-synaptically
367 (Zhang and Yuste, in prep.). Consistent with this, bath application of the neuropeptides Hym-248 can
368 trigger somersaulting, a complex locomotive fixed-action pattern [12].

369 While one could argue that these examples of non-synaptic neuropeptide actions are all from non-
370 bilaterians and may not be generalizable to other animals like bilaterians, it is also demonstrated that sys-
371 temic applications of neuropeptides can generate behavior in many animals, including primates, where
372 even inhalation of oxytocin has significant effects on social behavior [94] and is being explored for ther-
373 apeutic reasons in humans [95]. One should therefore consider the possibility of a “*hard*” *neuropeptide*
374 *hypothesis*, where non-synaptic actions of neuropeptides directly mediate behavior. Rather than playing
375 an accessory modulatory role on brain circuits, non-synaptic actions of neuropeptides could be the an-
376 cestral form of neuronal communication, as a basic chemical “chassis” of all nervous systems, whereby
377 synaptic release may have co-evolved to control or harness these neuropeptide networks for enhanced
378 speed and computational complexity.

379 Although obviously both synaptic and non-synaptic communications are at work in most nervous sys-
380 tems, the emphasis on synaptic transmission may have been overstated and synaptic transmitters could
381 often act via underlying multilayer chemical networks. Indeed, perhaps the metaphor of neuronal as elec-
382 tronic circuits that are computing, as if they were digital computers, could be fundamentally flawed, as it
383 overlooks what could be a critical role for chemical signaling. From this point of view, the current empha-
384 sis on the connectomics description of the wiring of nervous system should be complemented with the
385 systematic description of the “chemical”, or “wireless” connectome, where the chemical networks, based
386 on agonist-receptor matching, could reveal a missing layer functional diagram of neuronal interactions
387 using chemical signaling. Indeed, attempts to build such chemical connectomes based on neuropep-
388 tides and deorphanizing GPRs are underway in many species, including, *Nematostella* [18], nematode

389 worm [31], *Drosophila* [30], *Platynereis* [29], and mammalian neocortex [24], and could be very helpful
390 in deciphering the normal and pathological functions of the nervous system.

391 Finally, a neuropeptide based mechanism of behavior has also a strong evolutionary rationale, as it would
392 enable the “one stop shop” direct encoding of behavior using a single molecule, or gene, as opposed
393 to having to encode the specificity of complex synaptic circuits, thus facilitating the rapid and flexible
394 mutational sculpting of behavior by altering the structure or expression of neuropeptides, their processing
395 or their cognate receptor subunits.

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403 **Declaration of interest**

404 none

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